

Figure S1. Structure and activity data (EC₅₀ and CC₅₀) of Z-Tyr-Ala-CHN₂ ($n = 2$) and its analogues ($n = 1$) derived from the primary screen in VeroE6-eGFP cells. EC₅₀ values were obtained from a CPE reduction assay against SARS-CoV-2. CC₅₀ values were obtained from the toxicity counter screen which was performed on the same cell line using the ATPlite readout. n indicates the number of independent experiments.

Figure S2. Z-Tyr-Ala-CH₂ does not inhibit SARS-CoV-2 infection in an upper respiratory tract model. HNEC ALI cultures were infected with the indicated isolates and treated with PF-07321332 at 2.5 μM (red) and Z-Tyr-Ala-CHN₂ at 20 μM (black). Cell control (CC; grey bars, DMSO 0.2%). Virus control (VC; blue bars, MOI 0.1 without compound). The mean ± SD from within one representative experiment is shown. Within each experiment, conditions are performed in duplicate. DMSO, dimethyl sulfoxide.

Figure S3. Enzymatic Cathepsin L assay demonstrating that both Z-Tyr-Ala-CHN₂ and K777 inhibit Cathepsin L with EC₅₀ < 0.05 µM. Leupeptin, an inhibitor of endosomal trypsin-like serine and cysteine proteases, was included as a positive control, whereas water was included as a negative control. The graph represents one experiment performed to confirm observations from literature.